

Self-Injurious Behaviour in an Adult with Autism Spectrum Disorder

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Abstract

Self-injurious conduct is a highly maladaptive behaviour that is often associated with severe mental retardation and autism. Research has highlighted the complexity and multifactorial nature of the aetiology of the disorder. In this paper we present, after careful analysis, the treatment of an adult subject with autism spectrum disorder to reduce self-injurious behaviour and teach him more effective and less disabling 'coping strategies'. The experimental design used is of the criterion-variant type. The analysis of the data showed that the goals set were achieved. In the post-treatment sessions, we achieved extinction of the target behaviour.

Introduction

Autism Spectrum Disorders (ASD) are a set of different neurodevelopmental alterations linked to a normal brain maturation that most likely begins before a child is born, even if it occurs by the age of three. They are characterized by impaired communication and social interaction and the presence of restricted and repetitive interests and behaviour [1, 2]. Epidemiological data indicate the presence of approximately one person with autism for every 50 individuals, with a ratio of 4:1 between males and females [3].

The characteristics of clinical symptomatology can be extremely heterogeneous in terms of both complexity and severity and may vary in expression over time. Moreover, persons on the autism spectrum may present different neurological, psychiatric and medical co-morbidities, which it is crucial to consider when organizing interventions, and also different problem behaviours (self-injury, hetero-aggressiveness, compulsivity, hyperactivity, etc.) that are of great concern to teachers, therapists and caregivers and, often, create social stigma.

Problem Behaviours Associated with Autism

Problem behaviours' belong to a class of behaviours that are not considered relevant to the context in which

the individual is found, they can be defined as behaviours of such intensity, frequency or duration that they endanger the physical safety of the person or others, or behaviours that seriously limit the person's access to common settings, activities, services and experiences [4, 5].

Generally, this class interferes with the learning and socialization process, creating uncomfortable situations. However, this hindering and interfering role in development is not always well understood, especially when placed within a properly psychopathological view. Moreover, one must consider that the behaviours that we call 'problem' are often the best strategy that the person has elaborated to deal with a given situation. They can present themselves according to two different types [4]:

- *Transient*: Episodes that, mainly linked to environmental factors, have a strong character of unpredictability based on the person's habitual conduct; and present themselves as rare or very low frequency phenomena;
- *Stabilized*: Episodes that may be due both to environmental factors and to factors 'internal' to the person and present themselves as persistent phenomena over time or at a very high frequency. Stabilized 'maladaptive' responses may originally

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Autism Spectrum Disorder, Self-injury, Problem Behaviour, Differential Reinforcement of Other Behaviours (DRO), Systematic Desensitization.

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develop in each context and with certain contingencies and, subsequently, be maintained because of associated *secondary effects*, developing through gradual 'shaping' of responses, through mainly social contingencies. The assessment, therefore, should focus on the following factors: 1) identifying early types of behaviour that share similar aspects with severe problem behaviours, but which may be of lesser intensity and without causing, for example, tissue injury (lightly banging one's head on objects, biting without leaving teeth marks, scratching without necessarily tearing the skin, pulling one's hair without causing oneself pain, etc.), called 'pre-maladaptive behaviour', and 2) demonstrate that these acts are linked to environmental contingencies: the same behaviour can have different functions depending on the antecedent conditions ([6, 7, 8, 9].

As can easily be guessed, the person, from the numerous repetitions of associations between events (antecedent-consequences), learns to use behaviour to exert control over the environment: that is, he learns 'strategies' (the inadequate behaviours) through which he can regulate and/or control contextual events. These processes of regulation and control seem to imply [10]: 1) personal satisfaction (self-assertion); 2) access to otherwise unattainable reinforcers; 3) an 'escape way' in the face of untenable situations; 4) increased sensory 'activation'; 5) a 'shift' of attention away from endogenous causes; 6) a communicative mode; 7) a conditioned response to events occurring in other spheres and at other times.

These implications are not mutually exclusive but may even all be relevant to the same behaviour. Hence the need, not only to understand why certain manifestations occur, but also what are the antecedent and consequent conditions that determine the 'explosion' of the behavioural crisis that, being often destructive towards oneself, such as self-injury, and difficult to control, represents the 'problem behaviour' that so worries teachers, parents and therapists. Self-injury is always an indication of a high degree of distress on the part of the subject manifesting it, and this is true regardless of how the behaviour manifests itself (hitting oneself, pulling one's hair, biting oneself, etc.) [11, 12, 13].

Self-Injury

As we have seen, among the various maladaptive behaviours associated with autism (stereotypies, obsessivity and compulsivity, eating disorders, hyperactivity, acting-out, hetero-aggressiveness, etc.), self-injury (biting one's hands and arms, hitting oneself, banging one's head against furniture and walls, pulling one's hair out, ingesting inedible substances and objects, etc.), due to its characteristics, is very often the greatest concern for teachers and parents. Self-injurious behaviour is common in the population

with ASD, with an estimated prevalence of 42% [14].

Researchers have been investigating the causes of this problem for more than 40 years. Although the aetiology is still unknown, there is research and scientific evidence indicating the possible involvement of several factors, both organic and environmental, that are not mutually exclusive and may be interacting [15, 27, 31]. The first of these hypotheses refers to neurological or biochemical imbalances present in the Central Nervous System (CNS) of some individuals (*organic hypothesis*). According to this hypothesis, the levels and action of certain neurotransmitters (e.g. dopamine) in specific areas of the CNS (e.g. the basal ganglia) would be indispensable for maintaining an optimal level of reactivity to internal/external stimulation [16]. From this point of view, the organism of these subjects would react paroxysmally even in 'normal' situations. Thus, self-injurious behaviour would represent an extreme way of eliminating the constant feeling of pain. This hypothesis has received support using dopamine agonist and antagonist drugs that, in some cases, have produced changes (positive and negative) in self-injurious behaviour. The endorphin hypothesis also belongs to this group of hypotheses. According to which the non-natural release of endorphins following self-injurious and/or stereotyped behaviour would constitute an endogenous negative reinforcement for these otherwise painful behaviours [17, 18].

Other hypotheses that have found partial empirical confirmation come from the field of psychology. These hypotheses consider the possibility that the behaviours under study derive directly from the use of strategies to 'compensate' for sensory deficits, at peripheral and central levels, that prevent normal adaptation to the living environment (*'homeostatic' hypothesis*). According to this hypothesis, the Central Nervous System (CNS) would need an adequate level of endogenous and exogenous sensorial stimulation that, in subjects with autism, cannot be achieved [19].

Another hypothesis that has found considerable empirical confirmation is *the 'communicative' hypothesis*: self-injurious behaviour represents an extreme attempt to communicate one's needs [20].

Then there are the hypotheses that are closely related to forms of 'social learning' (*positive reinforcement hypothesis, negative reinforcement hypothesis*). This theory takes both extrinsic and intrinsic reinforcement into account. In the first case, reinforcers come from people, situations and events in the external environment. In the second case the reinforcers are internal (pleasure, reduction of the state of anxiety, pain, etc.) [21].

In principle, due to their severity, self-injurious behaviour has the advantage of gaining the attention and activation of the people around the subject. In this way it would be possible to explain, rather than the

onset, the maintenance of self-injurious behaviour even where such behaviour would no longer exist.

Methodology

Subject

Paolo is a 25-year-old adult suffering from autism spectrum disorder (Level 2: DSM-5) accompanied by a mild intellectual disability. As he cannot formulate a complete sentence, he uses a few words without intonation to communicate, but in a functional way. Comprehension is good (at least about instructions or simple commands). Paolo does not appear motivated to relate and only greets when asked. The parents report that when he was about three years old, he started to engage in some self-injurious behaviour (hitting his face with his fists or banging his head against tables, walls, etc.) and that over time this behaviour subsided, but from adolescence onwards it became more frequent and intense. Over the years, the family has repeatedly tried to remedy this through various treatments: pharmacological (anxiolytics, mood stabilizers, atypical antipsychotics, etc.), psychological (use of reinforcements, punishments, etc.), restraining (boxer helmets, arm bands, one of the parents' hands placed on his, etc.) and alternative (homeopathy, hippotherapy, etc.). The continuous failures of these strategies led to a deep conviction in the family members that treatment was impossible and, at the same time, to an increasingly evident and marked social isolation.

Since taking charge about two years ago, an attempt was made to identify, by direct observation of the subject, by interviews with the parents and by a similar functional analysis, the function of the self-injurious behaviour and after having excluded the conditions envisaged by this type of analysis (alone, contingent and non-contingent attention, required, tangible), the conclusion was reached that one of the prevailing components in Paolo's self-injurious behaviour was linked to 'anticipatory anxiety' [22, 25].

From functional analysis, direct observation and family reports we had obtained at least three elements to support this hypothesis: a) there was an increase in self-injurious behaviour when he 'thought', in the presence of a particular discriminating stimulus, that he would be in a particular frustrating situation in the future, b) the same happened when the subject found himself in new or unusual situations and c) when he perceived that the moment was coming when he would have to separate himself from the restraining object (headband, parents' hands, etc.).

Therefore, in order to better manage the considerable increase in anxiety and intervene on self-injurious behaviour, it was considered appropriate to implement two types of treatment: the first based on muscular relaxation; the second, on some *ABA-oriented* strategies: 1) the use of a visual agenda [4], 2)

differential reinforcement of other behaviours (DRO) [4] and 3) Systematic Desensitization [24].

About the first treatment, considered fundamental and indispensable to activate the second treatment, relaxation training, associated with correct breathing (inhalation and exhalation phase), was aimed at achieving a state of mental tranquility and muscular relaxation. The training consisted of purposely putting various muscle groups under tension (for about 10 sec.) and then relaxing them completely: hands and arms, shoulders and neck, forehead and face, chest and abdomen, legs and feet. In this specific case, the progressive muscle relaxation reworked by Bernstein, Borkovec and Hazlett-Stevens [23] was used, adapting it to the situation. In this way, Paolo learnt to recognize certain signs of physical tension and to use the perception of this tension as a signal to activate relaxation.

The first point of the second treatment was to identify some behavioural routines that the subject was activating in the context of the home and to organize a daily diary with images of the different activities to be carried out.

The visual agenda is a tool designed to determine a predictability of action, greatly reducing the anxiety of not knowing what will happen next, and was used to scan what will take place during the day, according to a spatial and temporal order. It was constructed with images according to the subject's abilities and needs, including the routine of removing the image of the activity that has ended, signaling the transition from one activity to another. Moreover, considering Paolo's characteristics and in order not to reinforce the repetitiveness and rigidity of the actions (routine), the *surprise card* (breaking the routine, proposing an unexpected activity), the *choice card* (the subject was invited to choose between two or more activities) and the *prize card* (presenting a pleasant activity to Paolo) were introduced (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: The Figure Shows Schematically the Structure of a Visual Diary in which the Cards

The figure shows schematically the structure of a visual diary in which the cards, which are much more, represent several daily routines that take place in a temporal succession. Once the activity has been performed, the corresponding card is removed from the diary and placed in a special binder, moving on to the next card. The *surprise* and *prize cards* are covered and remain so until the cover is temporally removed (it is not possible to do this earlier!).

The *surprise* and *prize cards* were covered and did not immediately reveal which activity was hidden; this strategy had a twofold purpose: 1) to favour waiting time, carrying out the other activities appropriately before arriving at the 'hidden' one and preventing anxiety from taking over and 2) to control, especially with breathing, the subject's state of anxiety not knowing what was hidden behind the *surprise* and *prize cards*.

This tool not only provided information on the organization of the day or part of it, but also enabled appropriate and effective planning and management of free time.

In the second point, an outstanding strategy was introduced to reduce or eliminate problem behaviour. This strategy is Differential Reinforcement of Other Behaviours (DRO), which consists of reinforcing the absence of the problem behaviour by sending it into extinction and is based on the principle that the programmed reinforcement can compete successfully with the effects of the inappropriate behaviour and can thus suppress it [26]. To use this procedure appropriately, we first established a time interval within which the subject never had to exhibit the unwanted behaviour to receive the reinforcement and gradually increased it according to his response. If Paolo exhibited the unwanted behaviour within the set time interval, we reset the stopwatch and restarted the count, and the subject only got the reinforcement after an interval completely free of the unwanted behaviour [4].

In the last point of the second treatment, *Systematic Desensitization* was introduced, a procedure in which an antagonistic anxiety response is presented in the presence of the anxiogenic stimulus, such that it causes the partial or total elimination of the anxiety response [24]. In our case it was used to habituate the subject to exposure to an unexpected test or a rather difficult request, inhibiting the evoked anxiety, through the induction of an antagonistic physical stimulus (breathing and relaxation).

To achieve this, the operator preliminarily constructed, on the basis of the subject's knowledge, a hierarchy of anxiogenic situations (starting from the least

anxiogenic), then inducing in the person a state of muscular relaxation (with the help of breathing and instructions taken from anxiety training) and when the state was obtained he presented the first stimulus of the hierarchy, asking the subject to signal (verbally or gesturally) both the perception of the stimulus and the first onset of the anxiety response.

In other words, as soon as the anxious response appeared, the operator would 'block' the exposure, removing the stimulus, and re-present the relaxation and, in the same manner, re-present the stimulus several times until the latency period, before the onset of anxiety, became longer and longer. At this point he would move on to the next stimulus in the hierarchy and repeat the entire operation until all situations were completely desensitized, taking care not to move on to the next stimulus if the previous one was not completely desensitized.

In this way, the anxious stimuli ceased to evoke avoidance behaviour and Paolo was able to face the previously feared situations without emitting self-injurious behaviour.

Experimental Design

To be able to check the effects of the educational intervention implemented on our patient we chose a Changing Criterion Design.

The first to use such a design in psychological and pedagogical experiments were Hall and co-workers [28, 29]; the method involves first of all assessing the behaviour on which one intends to intervene and then following the same intervention in several delineated phases, which is applied by taking a different success criterion for each phase [4]: in practice, once the basic level has been measured, an initial behaviour parameter is established, which is then met, another more demanding parameter is established, with each phase being taken as the basic level for the next phase. As soon as the rate of behaviour change responds to the set parameter the effectiveness of the intervention is proven [30].

Baseline

During the baseline phase, which was conducted in five one-minute sessions over 15 days, five self-injurious behaviours were defined and recorded (Tab. 1). At the end of the session the collected data were expressed by the number of times (frequency) Paolo hit himself.

The table 1 shows the measurements made during the baseline with respect to the three self-harm behaviours considered: Blows to the head, blows against 'physical elements', and attempted blows. The scores correspond to the average number of hits over the five daily sessions.

Table 1: Measurements Made during the Baseline with Respect to the Three Self-Harm Behaviours Considered

BEHAVIOURS	DAYS														
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
Blows to the head	67	64	65	67	66	63	64	66	69	65	65	65	65	68	67
Blows against 'physical elements'	3	5	7	7	6	5	6	6	5	7	7	6	6	5	7
Attempted blows	10	9	7	7	9	8	8	7	6	10	10	8	9	6	7
Total	80	78	79	81	81	78	78	81	80	82	82	79	80	79	81

To facilitate the task of those who had to observe and collect the data, blows to the head were all defined in the same way, whether they were delivered with the palm of the hand, fist or knee, or whether they hit the forehead, chin or ears. A separate category was reserved for blows delivered with the head against 'physical elements' (walls, furniture, door jambs, etc.) or against the chest of people trying to restrain it. Yet another category was represented by attempts that were unsuccessful because they were blocked in time by those assisting him.

During the time not under observation, the subject was contained by the caregivers, or by the caregiver, using the strategies that were normally activated, prior to the start of our intervention, to prevent him from causing injury or damage.

Treatment

The treatment initially consisted of teaching the subject to contract and decontract his muscles (relaxation), associating with this a perception of general well-being and improving breathing to control the tachycardia that was often the perceived signal (discriminating stimulus) for an anxious response that then resulted in self-harming behaviour. Subsequently the 'Visual Diary' was introduced to visualize all the day's activities in a temporal way, thus avoiding excessive anxiety states

not knowing what to expect; then 'Differential Reinforcement of Other Behaviours' (DRO) was used to reinforce the absence of self-harm behaviour and finally 'Systematic Desensitization' was introduced to gradually 'accompany' Paolo to better know how to manage his anxiety even in situations that were very destabilizing for him.

To achieve the goal of reducing or extinguishing these behaviours, a Changing Criterion Design [28, 29, 30] was implemented to immediately visualize the attainment of criteria lower than the baseline data. In fact, after the baseline was taken, it was established that Paolo had to hit himself 'only' 70 times (70: first criterion), i.e. about 10 fewer strokes than in the initial measurement; it must be borne in mind that the first criterion must be chosen appropriately in order to avoid the intervention itself becoming a source of anxiety for the subject; when the strokes consistently approached the established criterion, a new reduction in strokes was established (60: second criterion); when the strokes settling met this criterion as well, subsequent criteria were established, reducing them by 15 strokes at a time (45: third criterion; 30: fourth criterion; 15: fifth criterion), until the final goal (0 strokes) was reached.

Figure 2: Visualization of the Changing Criterion Design in a treatment to extinguish self-injurious behaviour

Note: BL = Base Line and FU = Follow-Up. The horizontal lines indicate the various criteria to be achieved

Results

The graph in Fig. 2 shows the trend in Paolo's self-injurious behaviour, which was significantly reduced from the early stages of treatment. This was because

the reduction in anxiety due to relaxation and breathing control had already resulted in better adaptation to environmental contingencies. Then with the use of DRO and Systematic Desensitization, there was a gradual but

steady improvement in behaviour to the extent that self-injury, which had become a 'coping' strategy for the person, was completely extinguished.

Conclusions

The results of this study suggest some potential targets for further study and provide a more comprehensive model of self-injury risk as a 'coping strategy' that some people may adopt to manage 'anticipatory anxiety'. This line of research should continue to better understand why self-harm occurs and who may be at risk for developing it chronically [32] and to intervene, with appropriate strategies, to prevent its occurrence [34].

In forty years of research in the field of developmental disabilities, several hypotheses have been formulated regarding self-injury, especially in autism spectrum disorder, which include both biological and behavioural factors [27, 31]. The latter have been extensively studied within the framework of applied behavioural analysis, which has provided rigorous evidence for the operant maintenance of this response. But even if self-injury is maintained by positive reinforcement, whether social or automatic, its onset may be substantially different from what causes its persistence and maintenance over time.

This suggests that future research on self-injury should refer to a model that includes both biological and behavioural characteristics [33].

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